

22RPT03 MultiFixRad

D7 - Preparation of the draft A for the Key Comparison EURAMET.T-K10

“Realisation of the ITS-90 scale over the range
from the Ag fixed-point to 2600 °C”

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1 INTRODUCTION:

Above the silver point (961.78 °C), the temperature is defined in the ITS-90 by extrapolation from the fixed point of silver, gold (1064.18 °C) or copper (1084.62 °C) using a radiation thermometer and Planck's law expressed in ratio form. The extrapolation introduces an uncertainty that increases with the square of the temperature ratio and therefore requires a thorough and accurate characterisation of the instrument, particularly its relative spectral responsivity and linearity. Behind its apparent simplicity, the ITS-90 is complex to realise and can only be implemented by laboratories with substantial resources.

The use of multi fixed points is an alternative method that allows calibration of a radiation thermometer over a wide temperature range without the need to characterise its spectral responsivity or linearity. However, the accuracy of the method depends on the distribution of the fixed points along the temperature range and the knowledge of their thermal properties, especially the emissivity and the melting phase temperatures.

The recent redefinition of the kelvin and its mise-en-pratique (MeP-K) is an opportunity to use high temperature fixed points (HTFPs) for the calibration of radiation thermometers as it enables the direct dissemination of the thermodynamic temperature by the means of HTFPs. Within the frame of the European projects InK (Implementing the new kelvin) and Real-K (Realising the new kelvin), thermodynamic temperatures have definitely been assigned (up to the next revision) to the following high-temperature fixed points: Cu (1085 °C), Fe-C (1153 °C), Co-C (1324 °C), Pd-C (1492 °C), Pt-C (1738 °C), Ru-C (1953 °C), Re-C (2474 °C) and WC-C (2748 °C).

2 GOAL OF THE COMPARISON – TRACEABILITY TO THE CCT-K10:

The aim of this comparison is to validate the capabilities of laboratories that have established references in the field of high temperatures. This validation will involve linking emerging laboratories in Eastern and Northern Europe to LNE-Cnam through the CCT-K10 key comparison [1].

The proposed comparison will consist of assessing ITS-90 scale realisations over the range from the silver fixed point up to 2600 °C, using a Chino IR-RST65H radiation thermometer as a transfer instrument. A transportable copper fixed-point blackbody source (IR-R0-AI) will also be provided to monitor the stability of the transfer radiation thermometer throughout the comparison.

The instruments and artefacts will be circulated in a semi-collapsed star ("flower") configuration, as described below. This approach enables the pilot laboratory to monitor instrument performance throughout the comparison and helps minimise issues related to incorrect operation or instrument drift.

Traceability of the participating laboratories to the CCT-K10 will be established by the intermediate of LNE-Cnam by combining the temperature difference between LNE-Cnam and the CCT-K10 reference value (RV), and the differences between each participating laboratory and LNE-Cnam. The uncertainty for each participating laboratory at each temperature will be calculated as the combined uncertainty of the laboratory itself, the uncertainty of LNE-Cnam in CCT-K10, and the uncertainty associated with the CCT-K10 reference value.

3 PARTICIPANTS:

All participants are from the Euramet region, the Regional Metrology Organisation of Europe. The details of NMI and contact person are given in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Participants for the key comparison

NMI or DI	Organisation legal full name	Address and contact person	Country
Cnam	Conservatoire national des arts et métiers	Laboratoire Commun de Métrologie 61, rue du Landy – 93210 La plaine Saint Denis – France Contact: Frédéric Bourson and Mohamed Sadli Email: frederic.bourson@lecnam.net Email: mohamed.sadli@lecnam.net	France
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DTU	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	Technical University of Denmark Anker Engelunds Vej 1, Bygning 101A, 2800 Kongens Lyngby, Denmark Contact: Andreas Næsby Rasmussen Email: anr@dfm.dk	Denmark
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4 COMPARISON SCHEME

The comparison was performed in two loops in the form of a semi-collapsed star, with an intermediate return of the artefacts to the pilot. The original comparison schedule had to be delayed due to technical preparations and approval by the CCT-WG-KC in October 2025.

Table 2: Original and actual measurement period schedules

Laboratory	Original measurement period	Laboratory	Actual measurement Period
Cnam	Dec. 24	Cnam	Dec. 24 and Jul. 25
DFM /DTU	April 25	SMU	Dec. 25
JV	May 25	RISE	Jan. - Feb. 26
RISE	June 25	Tubitak UME	March – April 26
Cnam	July 25	Cnam	May-June 26
CMI	Sept. 25	JV	Sept. 2026
SMU	Oct. 25		
UL	Nov. 25		
Tubitak UME	Dec. 25		
Cnam	Jan. 26		

5 CIRCULATING INSTRUMENTS

The circulating instruments are:

- a Chino radiation thermometer IR-RST65H supplied by LNE-Cnam (Table 2) hereafter referred to as “transfer radiation thermometer” or “Chino radiation thermometer”
- a Chino furnace IR-R0-AI including a Cu fixed point used to check the stability of the Chino radiation thermometer during transport and one spare Cu fixed-points supplied by LNE-Cnam (Table 3)

The technical specifications of each of the instruments are given in Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 3: Specifications for the Chino radiation thermometer

Chino transfer radiation thermometer	
Model	IR-RST65H
Serial number	IS-0246C0001
Spectral range	650 nm, FWHM 12 nm
Measuring temperature range	960 °C to 3000 °C
Distance Ratio (Distance / Target size)	650 (400 mm / Ø 0.6 mm)
Output	Voltage: 0 to 10 V Internal temperature monitor signal: 0 to 5 V (0 to 50 °C)
Focusing distance	400 mm to μ
Warm up time	Half a day
Power requirements	24 VDC, DC power supply (for 220-240 VAC) accompanies the instrument

Table 4: Specifications for the copper fixed point blackbody

Transportable copper fixed-point blackbody source	
Furnace model	IR-R0-AI
Serial number	AX021PA04-3
Fixed-point blackbody	Cu fixed point CuM7 + spare CuM6
Blackbody cavity	Ø 4 mm × 55 mm, with 120 °Conical end
Effective emissivity	0.9999
Plateau duration	Approximately 20 min
Heat-up time	Approx. 2 hours from room temperature to 1085 °C
Cool-down time	Approx. 2 hours from 1085 °C to 150 °C
Power	110-120/ 220-240VAC, 50 –60 Hz, 750 VA max
Gas requirements	Pure argon – flow rate 0.8 l/min
Temperature control	PID control by a pre-programmed controller

6 MEASUREMENTS AT THE PILOT LABORATORY (LNE-Cnam)

LNE-Cnam calibrated and characterised the Chino radiation thermometer. After the second loop finishes, the same validation will be performed. The characterisations consisted of:

- size-of-source effect measurements of the pyrometer
- range ratio measurements as appropriate
- validation of the transfer Cu fixed point source by direct comparison to the LNE-Cnam primary Cu fixed point

- measurement of the Transfer radiation thermometer outputs using the transfer Cu point (to provide a baseline reference signal)
- calibration of the Chino radiation thermometer over the full temperature range of the comparison, namely 962 °C, 1100 °C, 1300 °C, 1500 °C, 1700 °C, 1800 °C, 2000 °C, 2200 °C, 2400 °C and 2600 °C using the LNE-Cnam high temperature blackbody source and primary reference thermometer (radiance comparator)

When the instruments were returned to the pilot after the first loop, a validation was carried out in order to check the correct operation and stability of the instruments. These measurements were:

- verification of the operation of the transfer Cu fixed point using the LNE-Cnam primary Cu fixed point
- verification of the output of the transfer radiation thermometer using the melt/freeze transition of the transfer Cu fixed point source
- recalibration of the Chino radiation thermometer at the temperature points listed above, including check of the gain ratios

7 MEASUREMENTS AT THE PARTICIPATING LABORATORIES

Full details of the inspection and calibration procedure to be carried out at each participating NMI are given in the protocol for the comparison (Appendix 1). The measurements are summarised below:

- visual inspection of the packaging of the instruments on receipt of the cells and before shipment
- Measurement of the output of the Chino radiation thermometer by one melt/freeze cycle upon receipt and after completion of all other measurements before shipment to the next laboratory
- calibration of the transfer radiation thermometer, in terms of the ITS-90, at each of the calibration temperatures from 960 °C to 2600 °C (or to the highest temperature achievable within the participant's laboratory), using the ITS-90 realisation applicable to each participant
- measurement of the gain ratios
- any additional supplementary measurements forming part of the usual calibration procedure for a high-temperature radiation thermometer (for example measurements required for a full assessment of the calibration uncertainties)
- measurements of the lateral uniformity of the high-temperature furnace used for the calibration of the radiation thermometers in order to assess any additional corrections and/or uncertainty contributions

The participants provided the pilot with a report in the form of an Excel spreadsheet containing the calibration results and associated uncertainties, together with a Word document describing the equipment used and providing relevant details of the measurement method.

8 ANALYSIS OF FINAL RESULTS

8.1 Stability of the transfer radiation thermometer

Participants were requested to check the transfer radiation thermometer using the Cu fixed point provided with the instrument, shortly after receipt, and again at the end of the measurements before shipment to the next institute. Table 5 gives the temperature difference ΔT relative to the start of the comparison chosen as reference. V_{ref} is the response of the pyrometer at the start of the comparison, V_{lab} the response at measured at the participating laboratory, and $S_{pyrometer}$, the sensitivity of the pyrometer calculated by interpolation, the

instrument being calibrated at the Ag, Cu fixed points and against a blackbody set at 1100 °C. $S_{pyrometer} = 0,313$ mV/K.

$$\Delta T(mK) = 1000 \cdot \frac{(V_{lab} - V_{lref})}{S_{pyrometer}} \quad (1)$$

Table 5: Stability of the Chino radiation thermometer throughout the comparison. The temperature difference is calculated relative to the start of the comparison (10/07/2025)

Date	Laboratory	Chino pyrometer output voltage at Cu FP (dark current corrected) /mV	Temperature difference from start /mK
27/11/2024	Cnam	24.6935	-27
28/11/2024	"	24.6911	-35
09/07/2025	Cnam	24.7029	1
10/07/2025	"	24.7026	0
20/11/2025	SMU	24.6737	-10
09/12/2025	"	24.6773	2
15/01/2026	RISE	24.6733	-11
28/01/2026	"	24.6793	8
05/03/2026	Tubitak UME	24.6769	1
20/04/2026	"	24.6950	58

9 CONCLUSION

The EURAMET.T-K10 comparison started in April 2025. The comparison protocol was subsequently approved in October 2025, and the circulation of the instruments began in December 2025. The first measurement campaign involving the first three laboratories (SMU, RISE, and TUBITAK UME) has just been completed, with the instruments having been returned to LNE-Cnam for an intermediate calibration. The measurements associated with the second loop are scheduled for early 2027. The only results presented in this report concern the monitoring of the transfer pyrometer's stability. They are summarised in Table 5.